

Corneal abrasion

pharmacyinfoline March 8, 2024 2 min read

A corneal abrasion, also commonly called a scratched cornea, is an injury to the surface of the clear dome-shaped part of your eye called the cornea. It can happen very easily from something like a fingernail, a branch, or getting poked in the eye with another object.

Here's a closer look at corneal abrasions:

Symptoms:

- Pain in the eye, often described as a sharp, gritty, or burning sensation.
- Increased sensitivity to light (photophobia).
- Feeling like something is stuck in your eye (foreign body sensation).
- Blurred vision.
- Watery eyes.
- Redness in the white part of the eye [1].

Causes:

- Accidental contact with fingernails, makeup brushes, twigs, or other objects.
- Wearing contact lenses for too long or not cleaning them properly.
- Dry eyes.
- Getting hit in the eye with a sports ball or other object.
- Using eye drops that have expired.

Treatment:

Most corneal abrasions heal on their own within 1-3 days with proper care. Here's what you can do to help the healing process:

- **Apply artificial tears:** Use lubricating eye drops frequently to keep your eye moist and reduce discomfort.
- **Avoid rubbing your eye:** Rubbing can irritate the cornea and slow healing.
- **Pain relievers:** Over-the-counter pain relievers like acetaminophen or ibuprofen can help manage pain.
- **Avoid wearing contact lenses:** Stick to eyeglasses until your cornea heals completely.
- **Use an eye shield:** Your doctor may recommend wearing an eye shield to protect your eye while it heals.

See a Doctor If:

- You experience severe pain or vision loss
- The abrasion doesn't heal within a few days
- You have pus coming from your eye
- You have light sensitivity that significantly impacts your daily activities
- You suspect you have a foreign object lodged in your eye

Prevention:

- Be careful when handling sharp objects around your eyes.
- Wash your hands thoroughly before touching your eyes.

- Wear protective eyewear during sports or activities that could pose a risk to your eyes.
- Remove your contact lenses and clean them properly as directed by your eye doctor.
- Use lubricating eye drops if you have dry eyes.

By following these tips, you can help prevent corneal abrasions and keep your eyes healthy.

Suggested readings:

[Effect of drugs on rabbit eye: Pharmacology Lab Manual](#)

[Ocular Itching](#)

[Ophthalmic Preparations formulation considerations](#)

[Blepharitis](#)

[Myopia](#)